

Role of Spatiality in Rural-Urban Political Behaviour: A Socio-Economic Perspective

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ABSTRACT

Rural-Urban voters' representation and participation contrast has been viewed by many psephologist in terms of direct and undisputed connection with the spatiality resulting in behavioural changes. If there is any form of inequality, be it social, economic or political, prevailing in a section of society, it inhibits the real participation thus affect the true meaning of democracy. The article analyses the potential reasons for the occurring phenomena in a qualitative and quantitative manner. The data is based on the Lok Sabha elections 2014 and 2019 collected from Kheri Parliamentary Constituency. The paper tries to establish direct relationship between the rural-urban political dichotomy and explainable socio-economic or political causes for the same. The study finds that rural-urban political behaviour shows explicit variations. These changes have reasons ingrained in the different socio-economic lifestyles of the two regions.

KEYWORDS: Rural, Urban, Spatiality, Political Behaviour, Electoral Behaviour, Voting, Democracy

1. INTRODUCTION

Understanding democracy in terms of institutions and procedures which is supported by Schumpeter's definition of democracy as a competitive struggle for the popular vote¹ and further developed by Robert Dahl, who saw democracy as involving contestation or competition on the one hand and participation or inclusion on the other² is equally important on par with viewing democracy in terms of the social benefits that it can deliver where Tawney and Sen believe that this could be proved to symbiotic and make democracy more meaningful along with increasing living standards of citizens compared to other systems.³ Democratic virtues and democratic values constituting the base of political system can be effective mechanism to serve people in multi-cultural and diverse societies like India. Democracy which has both institutional and functional aspects, has been considered by many as a modern political tool to

¹ Joseph Alois Schumpeter, *Capitalism, Socialism and Democracy*, 5th ed. (Routledge, 1976).

² Robert Dahl, *Polyarchy* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 1971).

³ R.H. Tawney, *Equality* (HarperCollins Publishers Ltd, 1965); A. Sen, *Development as Freedom* (New York: Knopf, 1999).

manage diversities through presenting the absoluteness of the State and the government vis-à-vis citizens and creating both representative and participatory democracy. Representation and participation in real terms lies in the fact that active and passive franchise reaches to every citizen in a free, fair and impartial manner.

Though Spatial arrangements provides territorial speciation's⁴ but also it encompasses the definition and limits of the boundary of "social defense" and "offense" of a social form⁵ and spatial structure⁶.

⁴ N. J. Spykman, *The Social Theory of Georg Simmel* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press., 1925).

⁵ J. A. Agnew, *Political Geography: A Reader* (Arnold, 1997).

⁶ Ian Gregory et al., "Geoparsing, GIS, and Textual Analysis: Current Developments in Spatial Humanities Research," *International Journal of Humanities and Arts Computing* 9, no. 1 (2015): 1–14; Mohd Firoz Ahamed, *Space, Place and Global Capital: A Study of Transforming Indigenous Spaces.*, 1st. (New Delhi: Rawat Prakashan, 2019); Rusi Jaspal and Marco Cinnirella, "The Construction of Ethnic Identity: Insights from Identity Process Theory," *Ethnicities* 12, no. 5 (October 4, 2012): 503–30, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468796811432689>; Saddam Husain and Mohd Firoz Ahamed, "Place & Power: A Study of Kurdish Identity in Turkey," *GeoJournal* 87, no. 5

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Spatiality has always animated world politics. Spatial politics refers to the use of spatial terms to simplify and dramatize political differences and actions be it at Local, National or International level. In this context, works of Harvey (1985), Paasi (1991), Reynolds (1994), Leiter, H Sphered (2008), Ahamed (2019a) and Husain (2021) have conceptual contribution.⁷ Paasi explains how territorial significance goes through four phases and matures into a “Institutionalization a regional identity”, a result of socio-spatial process in which a territorial unit emerges as part of the spatial structure of the society concerned, becomes established and identified in various spheres of social action and consciousness, and may eventually vanish or deinstitutionalize in regional transformation. It is aided by the formation of regions’ ‘symbolic shape’, ‘emergence of institutions’ and completes with the institutionalization process involving the maintenance and continued reproduction of the region as a social entity. The region is now firmly established materially, socially and in the consciousness of its members and can be used for ‘place marketing,’ as a political weapon in struggles over resources and power, and as ‘the material ends to which state is applied’.⁸ Applying the context in terms of ethnicity, Husain (2021) concludes that identity, especially ethnic identity has an important relationship with the places that determine, define and pursue the dimension of the identity. On the other hand, these specific places project the power for preserving and recognising themselves in a context of social boundary differing to others.⁹

Rural-Urban voters’ representation and participation contrast has been viewed by many psephologist in terms of direct and undisputed connection with the

(October 1, 2022): 4235–49, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10708-021-10498-z>.

⁷ D. Harvey, *The Urbanization of Capital* (Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 1985); Anssi Paasi, “Deconstructing Regions: Notes on the Scales of Spatial Life,” *Environment and Planning A* 23, no. 2 (1991): 239–56, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1068/a230239>; David R Reynolds, “Political Geography: The Power of Place and the Spatiality of Politics,” *Progress in Human Geography* 18, no. 2 (1994): 234–47; Helga Leitner, Eric Sheppard, and Kristin M Sziarto, “The Spatialities of Contentious Politics,” *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers* 33, no. 2 (2008): 157–72, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1475-5661.2008.00293.x>; Mohd Firoz Ahamed, “Indigenous Group: A Study through Spatial Perspective,” *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 2019, www.jetir.org/view?paper=JETIR1903176; Husain and Ahamed, “Place & Power: A Study of Kurdish Identity in Turkey.”

⁸ Paasi, “Deconstructing Regions: Notes on the Scales of Spatial Life.”

⁹ Husain and Ahamed, “Place & Power: A Study of Kurdish Identity in Turkey.”

spatiality resulting in behavioural changes. Behavioural Geography advocates that the actions and mental states of individuals cause, and are caused by, physical and social environments, within the context of ongoing and changing interactions. These actions, reflecting in everyday political life around the world have been a central debate to understand *de causis* of rural-urban political vicissitudes. Around the world, there are plenty of political examples. Binary in India, Congress-Rural, BJP-urban have been much analysed and established. Notable political events in Europe, like the Brexit vote in the UK in 2016 and the Gilet Jaunes protests in France in 2018, have also highlighted the stark political differences between rural and urban areas. Numerous studies have shown how political politics in the US increasingly follow unique spatial patterns, with rural areas serving as the Republican base and nearly all big cities being Democratic strongholds.¹⁰ Some conclusive and clear conclusions have been made regarding the shortcomings of the literature that looked at the conceivable and likely reasons. Among other things, Bishop's (2009) research supported the sorting theory, which postulated that Americans were assembling into groups that most closely matched their political beliefs, way of life, and demographic background.¹¹ This further indicated at a strengthening of the lines dividing urban and rural populations. On the other hand, other academics contend that living in a rural or urban area has less significance now when analysing political outcomes. Sellers and others investigate the political behaviours of residents in metropolitan and nonmetropolitan areas. By emphasizing variations in professions, perspectives on traditionalism and materialism, and cultural variety, they contend that since the 1970s, urban political culture has become more and more dominant.¹² Last but certainly not least, current studies on the rural-urban continuum contend that as social and spatial borders are constantly blending,

¹⁰ James G Gimpel and Kimberly A Karnes, “The Rural Side of the Urban-Rural Gap,” *PS: Political Science & Politics* 39, no. 3 (2006): 467–72; Shannon M Monnat and David L Brown, “More Than A Rural Revolt: Landscapes of Despair and the 2016 Presidential Election,” *Journal of Rural Studies* 55 (2017): 227–36; Jonathan A Rodden, *Why Cities Lose: The Deep Roots of the Urban-Rural Political Divide* (Basic Books, 2019); Dante J Scala and Kenneth M Johnson, “Political Polarization Along the Rural-Urban Continuum? The Geography of the Presidential Vote, 2000–2016,” *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science* 672, no. 1 (2017): 162–84.

¹¹ Bill Bishop and Robert G Cushing, *The Big Sort: Why the Clustering of Like-Minded America Is Tearing Us Apart* (Houghton Mifflin Harcourt, 2009).

¹² Jefferey Sellers et al., *The Political Ecology of the Metropolis: Metropolitan Sources of Electoral Behaviour in Eleven Countries* (ECPR press, 2013).

shifting, and crossing, rurality is no longer a distinct sign of social inequalities.¹³ But the data on Lok Sabha Elections voting turnout in India supports the former argument and differs from the later. (Table 1) The urban voters in Indian politics have been found more dispirited and less active than their rural counterparts. The Why question is being answered from different perspective from time to time. A rational citizen who calculates the expected utility of voting may estimate that who wins will make some difference to him. But if the costs of voting are not negligible and the expected utility of voting is close to zero, the rational citizen should abstain.¹⁴ According to Anthony Downs, if a voter's vote value is more than zero—that is, if it is greater than the utility difference between the two candidates discounted by the voter's likelihood of having an impact on the result—they will cast a vote as instead of abstaining.¹⁵ Gordon Tullock further popularized the notion that the decision to vote appeared irrational on the face of it. People do vote presents a paradox in rational choice theory.¹⁶ There have been many reasons proposed for this: a concern to maintain a democracy¹⁷, a sense of duty¹⁸, the actions of group leaders or strategic politicians¹⁹, and the minimax-regret hypothesis of extreme risk aversion.²⁰

Blais and Young have suggested that for or most people, Voting is an unreflective and habitual act, based primarily on a sense of duty. But most citizens neither contemplate nor calculate costs and benefits when they think about going to the polls.²¹

¹³ Daniel T Lichter and David L Brown, "Rural America in An Urban Society: Changing Spatial and Social Boundaries," *Annual Review of Sociology* 37 (2011): 565–92; Scala and Johnson, "Political Polarization Along the Rural-Urban Continuum? The Geography of the Presidential Vote, 2000–2016."

¹⁴ John A Ferejohn and Morris P Fiorina, "The Paradox of Not Voting: A Decision Theoretic Analysis," *American Political Science Review* 68, no. 2 (June 1, 1974): 525–36, <https://doi.org/10.2307/1959502>.

¹⁵ Anthony Downs, *An Economic Theory of Democracy* (New York: Harper & Row, 1957).

¹⁶ Gordon Tullock, "The Paradox of Not Voting for Oneself," *American Political Science Review* 69, no. 3 (1975): 919.

¹⁷ Downs, *An Economic Theory of Democracy*.

¹⁸ William H Riker and Peter C Ordeshook, "A Theory of the Calculus of Voting," *American Political Science Review* 62, no. 1 (March 1, 1968): 25–42, <https://doi.org/10.2307/1953324>.

¹⁹ Carole Jean Uhlaner, "'Relational Goods' and Participation: Incorporating Sociability into a Theory of Rational Action," *Public Choice* 62, no. 3 (September 1989): 253–85, <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf02337745>

²⁰ Ferejohn and Fiorina, "The Paradox of Not Voting: A Decision Theoretic Analysis."

²¹ André Blais and Robert Young, "Why Do People Vote? An Experiment in Rationality," *Public Choice* 99, no. 1–2 (1999): 39–55.

This paper analyses the potential reasons for the occurring phenomena in a qualitative and quantitative manner and tries to establish direct relationship between the rural-urban political dichotomy and explainable socio-economic or political causes for the same.

1.1. India's Case: Voter's turnout

Turnout in the third-party system (1989–2009)²² averaged almost 59.1%, staying within this range once more. (Table 1) In both the 2004 and 2009 elections, turnout remained very stable, averaging 58 percent in the polls. From this angle, India saw its greatest voter turnout ever in 2014, at 66.4 percent, marking a clear break in the trend. This level of voter turnout was definitely brought about by two things: general dissatisfaction with the UPA government in power and enthusiasm for Narendra Modi's campaign. Corresponding data indicates that the constituencies where the BJP vote increased had the highest turnout.²³ 2019 saw again another record-breaking level of voter turnout, with 67.4% of eligible voters casting ballots, according to ECI data. The last two elections saw an average turnout of 66.8%, which clearly deviates from the previous third-party system. And, once again, it seems that the BJP benefited from higher turnout in 2019. For instance, the BJP-led NDA won 87% of seats in which voter turnout rose above 5% from 2014 levels, whereas it only won 29% of seats in which voter turnout fell below 5% from 2014. Voting turnout of rural and urban constituencies in India in General elections from 1977 to 2019 has witnessed an average of 4 points difference. This gap has gone up-to 14 points difference in 1999 elections.

²² Namely, in the third-party system, no national party served as the central gravitational force organizing politics. Electoral politics was marked by increasing party fragmentation, intensifying political competition, and a federalization of national politics.

²³ Milan Vaishnav, "From Cakewalk to Contest: India's 2019 General Election," April 16, 2018, <https://carnegieendowment.org/2018/04/16/from-cakewalk-tocontest-india-s-2019-general-election-pub-76084>.

Table 1: Showing Voting Turnout of Different types of Constituencies from 1977-2019 (All Figures in percent)

Voting Turnout	1977	1980	1984	1989	1991	1996	1998	1999	2004	2009	2014	2019
All Constituencies	65.5	56.9	64.0	62.0	57.0	58.0	62.0	60.0	58.8	58.2	66.4	67.4
Urban Constituencies	62.1	57.9	62.9	60.0	50.4	53.4	56.7	53.0	53.7	52	61	64.58
Semi-Urban Constituencies	60.4	57.8	64.8	62.7	56.8	59.0	62.9	61.5	59.1	61	69	66.67
Rural Constituencies	60.3	56.7	64.1	62.6	56.6	58.7	63.0	67.7	58.8	59	67	69.71

Source: Election Commission of India.

However, since 2009 the gap of the rural-urban turnout has been found to be shrinking standing at 7 points, 6 points and 5.13 points in 2009, 2014 and 2019 General elections respectively. It is very pertinent to note that rural turnout in General elections has been higher than the national level. This leaves an important question to ask and opens areas for further enquiry on why rural voters are better performers.

1.2. Social Differentiation and its link with Voting Behaviour

The differential and stratified society have created class, caste groups and strata based on religion, caste, gender, occupation and other bases that has led to different self-interests. The human being, on the behavioural part, sometimes acts as an individual, or sometimes it collaborates depending upon the nature of the motive. Naturally, Human is a social²⁴ and political animals²⁵. Human beings are a social species that rely on cooperation to survive and thrive.²⁶ People participate in an organization when they are going to gain something from them. People tend to identify themselves with the organization in which they participate. They also exhibit collective behaviour, which refers to relatively impulsive and unstructured ways of thinking and acting on the part of many people. Classic texts in political sociology saw elections as the expression of “the democratic class struggle”²⁷ between just two classes, the working and the middle. The Michigan Model stresses that class position helps account for perceptions and attitudes shaping political choices.²⁸

In India, the majority of voters are poor and illiterate due to their demographic makeup, and ethnic, religious, linguistic, and regional issues are given significant weight, which further limits the electorate's ability to behave rationally. Approximately 70% of Indian voters lack literacy, which limits their access to information and, consequently, their capacity to create perceptions. Also, rurality of the voters leaves them less economic opportunist and mobile than their urban counterparts. In the process of finding out how voters behaviour work, the importance of those direct factors positioning people in social class and status in a society cannot be compared less than demographic factors. Stating this fact, Popkin stated that “demographic facts provide a low-information shortcut to estimating a candidate's policy preferences ... characteristics such as a candidate's race, ethnicity, religion, gender, and local ties are important cues because the voter observes the relationship between these traits and real-life behaviour as part of his daily experience.”²⁹ The direct function of social status aided by the indirect role of urban-rurality of people shapes different social structures.

To understand how class and religion might influence political decision-making requires a grasp of the related but distinct notions of social and political cleavages. Political divides based on a society's socioeconomic structure are known as social cleavages.³⁰ It refers to differences in the political and social ideals that various social groups—such as social classes and ethnic and religious groups—hold. These differences may or may not be significant as the foundation for political rivalry and, consequently, political decision-making. In what way

²⁴ Shefali Jha, *Western Political Thought: From The Ancient Greeks to Modern Times* (Pearson India, 2018), 59.

²⁵ Stephen R L Clark and Stephen R.L Clark, *The Political Animal* (London: Routledge, 2002), <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203008119>.

²⁶ “The Cooperative Human,” *Nature Human Behaviour* 2, no. 7 (July 9, 2018): 427–28, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-018-0389-1>.

²⁷ Dewey Anderson and Percy Erwin Davidson, *Ballots and the Democratic Class Struggle; a Study in the Background of Political Education*. (Stanford University Press, 1943).

²⁸ Vincent L. Hutching and Hakeem J. Jefferson, “The Sociological and Social-Psychological Approaches,” in *The Routledge Handbook of Elections, Voting Behaviour and Public Opinion*, ed. Justin Fisher et al. (New York: Routledge, 2017).

²⁹ Samuel L Popkin, *The Reasoning Voter: Communication and Persuasion in Presidential Campaigns*, 2nd ed. (University of Chicago Press, 1994).

³⁰ Stefano Bartolini and Peter Mair, *Identity, Competition and Electoral Availability: The Stabilisation of European Electorates 1885-1985* (Cambridge University Press, 1990): 383.

Social cleavages are likely to have a large role in determining the makeup and tactics of political parties because political party conflict provide a platform for the expression of groups of people with shared interests or statuses, which are created by social structural inequities.

1.3. Tools and Method

The quantitative analysis examines the difference between rural-urban voting behaviour through the survey data conducted in Kheri Parliamentary Constituency, Uttar Pradesh, India for two General elections namely 2014 and 2019. The data of 386 respondents, collected through questionnaire, is processed through SPSS using two tests namely Chi Square test to test the association between variables and Cramer's V test to check the effect size of the Dependent variables. The proposed analysis opens up with some questions. It asks (1) what is the rural-urban behavioural change when it comes to Voting and other political decisions? (2) What is the effect size or magnitude of the rural-urban voting behaviour? (3) Is rurality only acting factor in voting behaviour or other socio-economic factors have also a say in changing or motivating the voters? Now the question arise that what is the basis on which behavioural comparison of rurality and urbanism can be analysed. For this purpose, the study adopts Sociological model of voting behaviour or Columian School. This school recognizes three elements: religion, socio-economic class or status, and place of residence, termed "Index of Political Predisposition" (IPP)³¹. For the convenience of this research, there are three bases taken to analyse rural-urban differentiation viz.

1. Socioeconomic conditions include age, gender, income level, marital status;
2. Work profile, and
3. Belief system.

The data has been stratified and analysed accordingly. The results extracted from the data are further utilized to test the hypothesis. Here, the whole analysis has been divided into four parts, viz; Descriptive Analysis, Factorial Analysis, Deductive Analysis and Hypothesis Testing and Results.

1.3.1. Descriptive Analysis

In this part, a brief profile of the respondents (Independent variables) has been given. Due to dominating rural proportion (~88%) of the Kheri District, among 386 respondents, rural and urban respondents are deliberately kept in the similar proportion. The brief profile constitutes Gender, Age, Education level, Religion, Caste, Sub-caste, Marital Status, Type of Family, Occupation, and Income Level in context of Rural or Urban based respondents in Table 2.

Table 2: Showing Socio-economic Data of respondents

			Locality		Total
			Rural	Urban	
Gender	Male	Count	232	34	266
		% of Total	60.1%	8.8%	68.9%
	Female	Count	101	19	120
		% of Total	26.2%	4.9%	31.1%
Total		Count	333	53	386
		% of Total	86.3%	13.7%	100.0%
Age	18-22	Count	10	0	10
		% of Total	2.6%	0.0%	2.6%
	23-34	Count	113	29	142
		% of Total	29.3%	7.5%	36.8%
	35-45	Count	127	15	142
		% of Total	32.9%	3.9%	36.8%
	46-59	Count	69	8	77
		% of Total	17.9%	2.1%	19.9%
	60-79	Count	13	1	14
		% of Total	3.4%	0.3%	3.6%
	80+	Count	1	0	1
		% of Total	0.3%	0.0%	0.3%
Total		Count	333	53	386
		% of Total	86.3%	13.7%	100.0%

³¹ Lazarsfeld, Berelson, and Gaudet, *The People's Choice*, 174.

Education	Illiterate	Count	83	0	83
		% of Total	21.5%	0.0%	21.5%
	Literate (Primary Education)	Count	44	5	49
		% of Total	11.4%	1.3%	12.7%
	Secondary Education	Count	75	2	77
		% of Total	19.4%	0.5%	19.9%
	Intermediate	Count	97	15	112
		% of Total	25.1%	3.9%	29.0%
	Undergraduate	Count	29	15	44
		% of Total	7.5%	3.9%	11.4%
	Postgraduate	Count	5	16	21
		% of Total	1.3%	4.1%	5.4%
Total		Count	333	53	386
		% of Total	86.3%	13.7%	100.0%
Religion	Hinduism	Count	233	29	262
		% of Total	60.4%	7.5%	67.9%
	Islam	Count	89	20	109
		% of Total	23.1%	5.2%	28.2%
	Sikhism	Count	9	4	13
		% of Total	2.3%	1.0%	3.4%
	Others	Count	2	0	2
		% of Total	0.5%	0.0%	0.5%
Total		Count	333	53	386
		% of Total	86.3%	13.7%	100.0%
Caste	General	Count	106	26	132
		% of Total	27.5%	6.7%	34.2%
	O.B.C	Count	145	24	169
		% of Total	37.6%	6.2%	43.8%
	S.C,	Count	81	3	84
		% of Total	21.0%	0.8%	21.8%
	S. T.	Count	1	0	1
		% of Total	0.3%	0.0%	0.3%
Total		Count	333	53	386
		% of Total	86.3%	13.7%	100.0%
Subcaste	Upper Caste	Count	116	28	144
		% of Total	30.1%	7.3%	37.3%
	Lower caste	Count	217	25	242
		% of Total	56.2%	6.5%	62.7%
Total		Count	333	53	386
		% of Total	86.3%	13.7%	100.0%
Marital Status	Married	Count	253	29	282
		% of Total	65.5%	7.5%	73.1%
	Unmarried	Count	37	22	59
		% of Total	9.6%	5.7%	15.3%
	Widow	Count	39	2	41
		% of Total	10.1%	0.5%	10.6%
	Deserted/ Separated	Count	4	0	4
		% of Total	1.0%	0.0%	1.0%
Total		Count	333	53	386
		% of Total	86.3%	13.7%	100.0%

Type of Family	Joint	Count	254	35	289
		% of Total	65.8%	9.1%	74.9%
	Nuclear	Count	79	18	97
		% of Total	20.5%	4.7%	25.1%
Total		Count	333	53	386
		% of Total	86.3%	13.7%	100.0%
Occupation	Agriculture	Count	70	4	74
		% of Total	18.1%	1.0%	19.2%
	Business	Count	63	14	77
		% of Total	16.3%	3.6%	19.9%
	Service	Count	12	10	22
		% of Total	3.1%	2.6%	5.7%
	Labour	Count	112	3	115
		% of Total	29.0%	0.8%	29.8%
	Other	Count	76	22	98
		% of Total	19.7%	5.7%	25.4%
Total		Count	333	53	386
		% of Total	86.3%	13.7%	100.0%
Annual Income	Rs.2500/- to Rs. 5000/-	Count	89	3	92
		% of Total	23.1%	0.8%	23.8%
	Rs. 5001/- to Rs. 7500/-	Count	115	7	122
		% of Total	29.8%	1.8%	31.6%
	Rs. 7501/- to Rs. 10000/-	Count	86	8	94
		% of Total	22.3%	2.1%	24.4%
	Rs. 10000/ and above	Count	43	35	78
		% of Total	11.1%	9.1%	20.2%
Total		Count	333	53	386
		% of Total	86.3%	13.7%	100.0%

Source: Primary Data created by author.

1.3.2. Factor Analysis

1.3.2.1. Reliability and Validity

Table 3: Reliability and Validity Summary

Case Processing Summary		N	%
Cases	Valid	386	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	386	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Table 4: Cronbach's Alpha Value

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.698	7

α (Alpha) Coefficient is used to measure internal consistency of data. It shows that how data are reliable. For this research, Cronbach's α for 7 items is .698 which are greater than 0.6 and acceptable.

1.3.3. Deductive Analysis

1.3.3.1. Test for Association between variables

We will examine the relationship between the independent and dependent variables in this section. This procedure includes the association test. It means the test will determine whether independent factors (Socio-Economic data) and dependent variables (Election behaviour, Political affiliation, and Media consumption) are correlated in any way.

1.3.3.1.1. Chi Square Test

To ascertain whether there is a relationship between two categorical variables, the test for independence—also known as the chi-square test of association or Pearson's chi-square test—is employed. Plotting the p-value against the significance threshold will show you if the variables are independent or not. Typically, a significance threshold of 0.05 (represented as α or alpha) is effective. A 5% chance of assuming there is an association between the variables when there isn't one exists is indicated by a significance level of 0.05.

P-value $\leq \alpha$ (Alpha; 0.05): There is a statistically significant correlation between the variables (Reject H0). The null hypothesis is rejected and it is determined that there is a statistically significant association between the variables if the p-value is less than or equal to the significance level.

P-value $> \alpha$ (Alpha): Unable to determine if the variables are related (failure to reject H0). You cannot reject the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than the significance level because there is insufficient data to draw the conclusion that the variables are related.

1.3.3.1.2. Test of strength

Effect Size (Cramer's V Test)- measure of the direction and strength of the relationship between two variables. As a measure of the relative (strength) of a link between two variables, it is interpreted. The coefficient is 0–1 on a scale. In actuality, you can discover that a minimal threshold of .10 for Cramer's V suggests a significant link between two variables.

$$V = \sqrt{\frac{X^2}{n(q-1)}}, \text{ where } q = \text{smaller \# of rows or columns}$$

Describing Strength of Association

Characterizations

- >.5 high association
- .3 to .5 moderate association
- .1 to .3 low association
- 0 to .1 little if any association

Table 5: Showing Association and Effect Size of variables.

Indicator	Association and Effect Size	Gender	Age	Education	Religion	Caste	Subcaste	Marital Status	Locality	Type of Family	Occupation	Annual Income
Voted not Voted	Association	Associated	Associated	Not Associated	Not Associated	Not Associated	Not Associated	Associated	Not Associated	Not Associated	Not Associated	Not Associated
	Effect size	Low	Moderate	Low	Little if any	Little if any	Little if any	Low	Little if any	Little if any	Low	Low
Vote affect	Association	Associated	Not Associated	Associated	Not Associated	Associated	Associated	Not Associated	Not Associated	Not Associated	Associated	Associated
	Effect size	Low	Little if any	Little if any	Little if any	Low						
Member of political party	Association	Associated										
	Effect size	Little if any	Little if any	Low	Low	Low	Low	Little if any	Low	Little if any	Low	Low
Free and fair Elections	Association	Not Associated	Not Associated	Not Associated	Associated	Not Associated	Not Associated	Not Associated	Associated	Not Associated	Not Associated	Not Associated
	Effect size	Little	Low	Low	Low	Low	Little if any	Low	Low	Little if any	Little if any	Low
Medium of information	Association	Associated	Not Associated	Associated	Associated							
	Effect size	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Moderate

Social Media Use	Association	Associated	Associated	Associated	Associated	Associated	Associated	Associated	Associated	Associated	Associated	Associated
	Effect size	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Low	Moderate	Low	Little if any	Low	Moderate
Fact-Checking Habit	Association	Not Associated	Associated	Associated	Not Associated	Associated	Associated	Associated	Associated	Associated	Associated	Associated
	Effect size	Little if any	Low	Low	Little if any	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low

Source: Primary Data extracted by SPSS.

Association and magnitude of association is important to check the electoral behaviour of the voters. The behaviour and habits were checked on the basis of seven questions asked in the questionnaire concerning whether (i) voters voted or not voted in the last two General elections 2014 and 2019; (ii) do the elections affect things in the country run; (iii) voters are members are affiliated to any political parties or groups; (iv) do voters think elections in the country are fair and free; (v) information medium of the voters; (vi) use of social media; (vii) do they fact-check information coming on social media?

The results (table 6) are depicted in the form of interpretation of the values (Annexures1 and 2) of the used tests to show the independence of variables and strength of association respectively.

1.4. Findings and Analysis

This section answers the questions raised in the beginning of this article. Coming to the first and second questions that is, to find the rural-urban behavioural change and its magnitude, the following results are elaborated accordingly.

1.4.1. Voting Turnout and How Vote Affects

The majority of respondents in rural (86.8%) and Urban (92.5%) were able to cast votes in the general elections of 2014 and 2019. This shows a Rural-Urban divide in voting turnout. Act of voting does not necessarily mean that voters are interested in politics and public affairs. Citizens have their way to contribute in the domain of public affairs. Some regard voting as the only political obligation of a citizen. Some only express views in support of ideology or political parties. Some engage with political parties directly by taking their membership and campaigning in elections. Among absentees during voting, most respondents in rural areas, 39.58% cited "Voter ID not Issued" as a major reason for not voting. Statistically, absenteeism is not associated with religion (Chi-Square = 0.055). Interestingly, voting decision is affected only by Gender, Age, and Marital status. Other socio-economic conditions and belief of the voter do not impact its decision to vote or not to vote. In measuring strength of association, all socio-economic indicators (namely, gender, age, education, religion, caste, subcaste, marital status, locality, type of family, occupation and annual income) lie between low to little associated except Age (Moderate association). (Table 6)

The respondents gave opinions on how act of voting affects things run in this country or do they think their vote make np difference. Among respondents from

rural background, a significant chunk of respondents (77.5%), believes that vote has value and somehow contributes in the developmental process of the country. However, among urban respondents, 81.1% gave node and says vote is effective. interested in the political affairs of the state or country. Notably, Gender, Education level, Caste/Sub-caste, Occupation and Income level of the voters aid them to build the opinion on this issue. (Table 6) Political affiliation is also expressed through the membership of political parties or organizations. Responses of respondents regarding association with political parties are recorded. Out of Rural respondents, only 6.9% were affiliated with any political organization in one way or another. In contrast, 93.1% of respondents had no affiliation. Likewise, among urban respondents, only 7.5% were affiliated with any political organization in one way or another. If to name political parties, the BJP has the most affiliated respondents 53.2% in urban. In comparison, the SP, the INC, and the BSP have 18.1%, 12.7%, and 10.1% affiliations among all urban respondents. Among rural respondents, only 25% are affiliated with the BJP. The SP, the INC and the BSP have 30%, 31% and 10% affiliations respectively. While measuring the association of SECs with party affiliations, it is found that all SECs are associated with it. However, the strength of the association is Little or low. That means all socio-economic conditions are factors behind voters' affiliations but not primary motivation.

The findings gave us a scope for the interpretation of results. The urban-rural political behaviour is found be different at many points as depicted above. The reasons for such variances should be understood in the terms of geo-spatial, political and socio-economic contexts. The voting habit and reasons of absence has

seen a clear demarcation between rural-urban settings. Rural voters, due to political insensitivities, exit in a group and act as a vote bank where they put their demands, or convey their needs through a intermediary. These intermediaries negotiate with the political parties on the behalf of 'invisible' vote bank.³² As voters move up the economic ladder, the need for intermediaries goes down. Reasons can be varying. The middle class that resides in urban or semi-urban India, is more aware with their rights. They are better educated, having their members in bureaucracy, direct connections with political parties in power or pressure groups. They believe in their ability to influence the system due to their civic consciousness. They use the communication machinery and other means of being heard, to reach their political representatives more easily and does not need a middle man or 'Pseudo representative of the community'. This increases their effectiveness and make them different than their rural counterparts. Uneven development leading to spatial differentiation (industries, jobs etc.), in continuum that difference, work nature was differentiated on explained by critical political economy theory.

1.4.2. Free and Fairness of Election Process

Free and fair system of electoral process is one of the cornerstones of democracy. Respondents were asked whether Indian elections are free and fair. Among the rural respondents, 79.9% were positive. In Urban section, only 64.2% believes the impartiality of the electoral process. Interestingly, Belief system and Locality is directly associated with this belief of the voters. However, all the socio-economic conditions are low or little associated. It means that concept of neutrality and fairness is more has to do with region of the voters depending on the local settings and environment and subjectivity of right and wrong is derived from the belief system of the voters. Urban has better mechanism of political accountability than rural due to their local proximity. In that process, the fairness, impartiality and effectiveness of electoral process can be checked more easily. Also, rural regions are inherently less aware with the rules, regulations and updates in the electoral process, thus affecting its ability to evaluate and question the electoral process, if needed.

Media is said to be the fourth pillar of democracy. In this study, our scope with media is limited to Print Media (Newspapers), Broadcasting Media (Television) and Internet Media (Social Media Apps). Its use has gone up in recent years. With the

increasing purchasing power and availability and accessibility of the Internet, the use of television, mobile phones and social media has gone up many folds. The source of information is an important aspect that psephologists cannot ignore. 46.9% respondents in rural section cited TVs as their sources of political news, while 42.2% use mobile phones for the same. The third highest source of information source is Informal groups, constituting about 33.5% of cumulative options.* (* % calculated for more than two options) However, in urban, the proportion of TV watchers and mobile phone-based information source increases to 78% and 88% respectively. The informal sources in Urban areas play less effective role and stand at only 30% only. All the SECs are found to be associated with sources of political news having low to moderate association. Social media penetration in society is increasing like never before. It has shifted society's information access and nudging in a different way. Of all smartphone users in urban, 95.7% use social media. It shows a significant rate of social media usage. While this using habit in rural section drops to 81%. All the SECs of respondents are associated with social media use. The magnitude of the association lies between low to moderately associated. In counting the kinds of social media apps used by respondents, it is found that WhatsApp has the highest number of users (91.4%). Facebook and YouTube are used by 64.5% and 89.2% in cumulative. 39.0% of respondents use other apps.* (* % calculated for more than two options) The variation in rural and urban in terms of information building process could be explained in terms of different economic and social patterns emerging due to spatiality. The forms of work and patterns of social stratification in rural areas should be a source of difference in voting patterns. Rural sociologists often point out how structural statuses and the nature of work imbue people with different lived experiences, worldviews, and political and economic interests.³³ Urban regions have better job prospects. Rural people migrated in search of better opportunities. Due to this rural demographic finds more older and women in rural India (leaving migration due to marriage). The patriarchal society and inherent limitations of old age drags behind the rural people in technically advancement. This starts the vicious cycle of less informative and thus supporting the grapevine system.

Fake news and rumours have made it hard to differentiate between authentic and fake news. When

³² MN Srinivas and M Marriot, "The Social System of a Mysore Village in Village India. Studies in the Little Community," *The American Anthropologist* 57, no. 3 (1955): 31.

³³ Cynthia M Duncan, *Worlds Apart: Poverty and Politics in Rural America* (Yale University Press, 2015); Jennifer Sherman, *Those Who Work, Those Who Don't: Poverty, Morality, and Family in Rural America* (University of Minnesota Press, 2009).

asked, 72.8% of rural respondents said that they believe election-related information that comes on social media. While fact-checking habit in urban areas is more prevalent where more than 48.7% respondents accepted that they fact-check before believing the information is true. All the SECs are little or low associated with the factor, which means all respondents, irrespective of their SECs, behave similarly when checking the genuineness of the election news. This reiterates the fact that rural regions are less sources to crosscheck information due to their traditional ways of information seeking and opinion making.

1.5. Conclusion

Shifting development debates from holistic approach towards more decentralised and localised has uncovered the neglected domain of regional inequality and its long-term repercussions on social-economic and political life of its stakeholders. Making arguments in support of merging and fading rurality and urbanism into one, in the veil of traditions, infrastructure and so on, can only be temporary trends because opinion and behaviour of people are shaped by their daily socio-economic practices, problems, challenges. The urban life is characterised by cultural diversity whereas rural community shows we-feeling, territorial inclusiveness and self-sufficiency. The heavily one-sided economic development has stretched the dyke of inequality. This is why son of soil theory could be seen more prevalent in rural voting behaviour due the fact that rural India has been neglected by the politicians in comparison to urban giving urban has more opportunities, economic interests and development goals. This argument justifies the symbiotic relation of democracy and its social benefits discussion in beginning of the paper. Visibly, the rural-urban behavioural changes have direct connection with the socio-economic conditions prevalent in their respective regions. These regional imbalances have the answers to political experts and psephologists on the policy decisions and their role in understanding the political behaviour and patterns.

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